

GOOD NAMING THE ATTRACTIVE CITY = PANORAMIC VIEW OVER THE CITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371657>

Annotation: This article provides information about the absurdity of naming cities and disrespect for native language, the fact that some city names are given in a fancy way, and they gave several description of the semantic meaning of some of the world's cities. Through the article, the authors tried to describe to the readers that the damage of the Uzbek language is not well and that it is disrespectful to our great ancestors.

Key words: city, naming, famous names, developing scale, Semonemics, Temirids' town, State Language, nor spelling standards, nor national values.

Introduction. Accordance of the processes of globalization and integration, the development of modern science and technology, and the continuous application of ICT in the fields of production, at the beginning of our century, humanity entered a new era of its development. As a result, the world is changing rapidly today. Unbelievable innovations are happening in the political, economic, cultural and household life of the states. From this comprehensive process, "From national revival to national rise!" The ancient and modern Turanian land, which entered its Third Renaissance under the motto, is not an exception to the state of Uzbekistan. States and peoples are choosing their own path in order not to be pushed out of the stage of history and to "survive" among others in the current dangerous times. In this regard, we all know how correct the policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is, based on justice, humanity, tolerance, peace and tranquility. Our national values, our immortal traditions inherited from our high-minded ancestors play an important role in all our activities in the country and abroad. At the beginning of our values is always our proud servant, humble mother tongue.

Method. Alongside with semantic analysis, contrastive typological, observation and interpretation, comparative contextual analysis as well were used.

Discussion. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev said in his speech at the ceremony dedicated to the thirtieth anniversary of the granting of the state language status to the Uzbek language: "Our mother tongue is an inexhaustible source of our national spirituality. Therefore, it is not only our task, but also our sacred human duty to show him the respect and honor he deserves," he said in context of his speech. PL-5850 of the head of our state dated October 21, 2019 "On measures to fundamentally increase the prestige and position of the Uzbek language as a state language" and PF-5850 dated October 20, 2020 "On measures to further develop the Uzbek language and improve language policy in our country" Decree No. 6084 serves as a program.

It is impossible to believe the great creativity in our country. Magnificent buildings, enterprises and organizations, firms, shops, which are rising equally in all regions, are a sight to see in our country. Especially in this regard, the experience of the capital city of Tashkent is becoming an example for everyone. The houses and buildings that is being created are an

expression of the strength of our nation, the results of the hard work and dedication of our selfless people. At this point, "Well, are the labels, titles, names, and slogans appropriate for the buildings?" Was the requirements of the official language followed in naming? It is natural that questions arise. Because, we know that in any name, the nation's history, spirit, spirituality, dreams, goals and tasks were reflected. To be honest, we have achieved the achievements of the people of the world in a very short time in the fields of architecture, construction, and urban planning, but in the names and inscriptions on the facades of buildings, disrespect for the mother tongue, artificial names, imitation, and one-sidedness are still visible.

Let me give one example. Successful entrepreneurs, business managers to their enterprises *TRADING AND IMPEX, AGRO LIMON SERA, IN VITRO VERITAS, AL SOHIB TRANS, SAMIR MUHLIS MUNIR, HASANHAMRO FAMILY CO, GIGANT SOF TRANS, SAB'A-7, AL'FA, FAX-KONIG, Vadiy shaslik hause, Sariq bola pizza style*. These names do not meet the requirements of the state language, nor spelling standards, nor national values!?

Our ancestors were clever in naming! Names like *Shaikhontahur, Kokcha, Khadra, Chorsu, Registan, Shahi Zinda, Tillakori madrasa, Chashmai Ayub, Samoniyyir mausoleum, Ichan Qala, Kalta minor, Polvan gate, Kokhna ark, Pahlavon Mahmud's wall* were destroyed by them. Couldn't go? Where is the experience, traditions, deep thinking left from the ancients?! After all, the best aspects of them always came to our blood?! What happened to us?! Foreign advertisements, foreign writings that are lit day and night, dazzling in the dark nights, have dazzled our eyes?! Do we want an example from them?! Where did the prestige and honor of the state language go? In our article, we tried to find answers to these questions, to show achievements and shortcomings on the example of names in *Shayhontahur and Chilanzor* districts.

First of all, let's talk about the science of nomination norm of the cities. At the beginning of the 21st century, the advanced countries of the world responded to the rapid, modern requirements of naming from the stage of onomastic (Greek onomastics - the art of naming, the art of name), which is the branch of linguistics that studies all famous names, the history of their emergence and change, as well as the sum of all famous names. has passed to a new stage of quality - nomination, which fully meets the demands of consumers. The art of naming (English naming) has appeared in world science and is developing on a large scale. This goes back to modern marketing, marketing, and market economy, production of goods, advertising, sales, urban planning, the beauty of cities, the use of ICT in production and several other factors.

Semonemics, image making, copywriting, (advertising text), and brandology fields are also rapidly developing as accompanying concepts. Among them is seminemics (Greek *semon* - sign + name in - designation) - the art of creating original commercial names and names to identify companies, goods or services.

How is this process going for us?

Tashkent, as the center and capital of our Republic, should be an example to other regions in following the standards of the current Uzbek literary language, promoting and protecting it. It would be a good thing if any good work on the state language started in Tashkent and spread to all regions. Including naming enterprises, organizations and institutions. Tashkent has centuries-old experience in this field. Names such as *Eski Jova, Oktepa, Akilon, Labzak, Chilanzor, Darkhan, Shirinquduq, Pushtibog, Karatash, Koshtut,*

Beshyogoch, Anhon, Khichqiriq, Bozsuv, Jarariq, Borijar, Chukurkoprik are from the deep thinking of the people of Tashkent, the eternal history, the unique culture and lifestyle. is evidenced by its aspects.

Shaikhontahur and Chilonzor districts are considered the heart of Tashkent. Therefore, the names here should be rich in national values, resounding, attractive, and clearly show the real situation and the intensity of the times. There are many such names in both districts. Looking at them, you can feel that we are living in Uzbekistan and that the reforms are having a strong effect. This is the case in most state organizations and institutions. For example: *Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Agency of Automobile Transport of Uzbekistan, National Agency "Uzbekkino", "Uzbekistan-Germany" Education Society, State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Youth Union of Uzbekistan, Ministry of Agriculture and Water Management of the Republic of Uzbekistan, International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan, State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, Children of the Republic "Barkamol Avlod" center of artistic creativity, public fund of kindness and health of Uzbekistan*, etc. The analysis shows that such warm words cannot be said about the names of companies, limited liability companies, and non-governmental non-profit institutions operating in both districts. True, among the given names there are also those that give the air of Tashkent and meet the requirements of the state language. This includes such LLCs as *"Golden Dome", "Spring Colors", "Shodlik", "Kokcha", "Mitti Star", "Anhor Saili", "Ikhtisos va Ilm", "Mashriq Mashali", "Sharq Mayogi"* We can mention NTM names such as *I", "Wise youth"*, but they do not make up even half a percent of the total stock of names. The rest are names consisting of English, Russian, Arabic, Turkish words and Uzbek words that do not fully meet the standards of the current Uzbek literary language, our spirituality, national values, and have not yet assimilated into our vocabulary.

Article 19 of the Law "On the State Language" states that "Seals, stamps, and documents of institutions, organizations and public associations shall be in the state language." As the Uzbek language is recognized as the State language of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is guaranteed that it will not hinder the functioning and development of other languages on the territory of the republic, and the free communication of representatives of all nationalities living in Uzbekistan in their native languages. Articles 2, 4, 6, 10, 14 of the law show respect and deep respect for the languages of representatives of other nationalities. This shows how impartial the Law "On State Language" is. But who are the organizations operating under such names as FMGH-West national investment, "Albatross consulting" law office, "Legal development" law office, and "Sultanov and partners" law office serving? To citizens of Uzbekistan or to foreign guests?

Republic of Uzbekistan No. 311-II- "On Limited Liability and Additional Liability Companies" published on December 6, 2001, O'RQ-51- "On Company Names" dated September 18, 2006, "On Non-Governmental Non-Commercial Organizations" dated April 14, 1999 Laws No. 763-I did not take into account aspects related to the name. At that time, problems related to our spirituality, culture, history, and national values were being solved. It did not occur to anyone that there was politics and some ideology under the simple name. That's why officials unknowingly chose names that looked beautiful to their eyes, especially those made with the participation of international words, as names for their companies and organizations. This process is still ongoing.

It is necessary to think seriously about the names of non-state commercial centers, limited liability companies, and companies. The analysis shows that names such as "Abdusalam Abad Trade" LLC, "Chorsu Fayz Trade" LLC, "Qaratut Ibrat Servis" LLC, "Nur-Ergash-Savodo" LLC, "Qanot Sharq" LLC are just a combination of simple words. Names like "Alimardan baraka goyib" LLC are melting. Our ancestors never gave such a name.

"Ali brand" LLC, "Jamshid food" LLC, "Makhmudov foods" LLC, "Marvarid-art group" LLC, "As kurilish sifat" LLC, "Vi-va travel" LLC, "Afsona child" LLC, "Viza- "viz plus" LLC, "Guncha elit" LLC, and the words brand, food, art, child, Viza-viz, elite were used inappropriately.

"Boqi-gold" LLC, "Babur-prins" LLC, "Farangis star" LLC, "Gold business guarantee" LLC, "Hasan decor" LLC, "Jam-sheer" LLC, "Feliz tea" LLC, "Clean city" KHUJMSH, Yusup build, "Atlas education" NTM, "Montessori-telim" NTM, "Omad kaliti plus" NTM, "Ziya study" NTM, "Nilufar elit inter education" NTM, "Yusuf study" NTM, "Ahad Qayum star" NTM, "Orient education" NTM, "Shahzoda study" NTM, "Dildar education center" NTM, "Hijama school" NTM, "Kadirov medical service" LLC, "Doktor madad farm" LLC, Sharop med-farm" This can be observed in names such as LLC, "Lobar Plus Farm" LLC.

"Richmond trust" NTM, "Future generation" NTM, "Oriental classic study" NTM, "Highest infant group" NTM, "Accounting and business courses" NTM, "Kid's future" NTM, The international cultural center of Tashkent" NTM, " Empire" NTM, "Kid's future" NTM, "Travel study" NTM, "Gle servis plus" NTM, "Essential study" NTM, "Friendship language bridge" NTM, "Fair view" NTM, "Psychological language bridge" NTM, " Unique education" NTM, "Express education study" NTM, "Campus challenge" NTM, Go ahead" NTM, "Aspiration" NTM, "London English school education" NTM, "Forward education" NTM, "Super study" NTM, "Harvard education" NTM, "Standard press" NTM, "Modern minds" NTM, "Insight education" NTM, "Kids land step" NTM, "Education prosystem" NTM, "Golden bridge education" NTM, "Get innovative club" NTM, " Indigo land" NTM, "Big way study" NTM, "Lingvo land" NTM, "You matter group" NTM, "Knowledge treasure" NTM, "It support professional education" NTM, "Perfect stand" NTM, "Intellect active" NTM , «Creative study group» NTM, «Skill set» NTM, «Lifelong learning» NTM, «Intension education» NTM, «Euro study» NTM, «English friends» NTM, «Wise training center» NTM, «Holy land-esthetic » NTM, "Oxford language center" NTM, "Brilliance learning center" NTM, "Education house" NTM, "Kindergarten" NTM, "Fine study" NTM, "Top step" NTM, "Training house" NTM, "Western academy" NTM, "Happybaby" NTM, "Record-education" NTM, "Lead academy" NTM, "Imperial elite" NTM, "Ace-school" NTM, "Light house" NTM, "Kids oxford" NTM, ""Super subject" NTM, "Dream school" NTM, "Express learning" NTM, "Best school" NTM, "Small jenaus" NTM, "Smart plus trading" LLC, "Regal globe service" LLC, "Best boss tex" LLC, "Asia green food" LLC, "Big trans max servis" LLC, "Gold fish product plus" LLC, you don't even know where you live (!)

The English words in the names have not yet been included in the 5-volume "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language"?!

It is disrespectful to our history to name one's organization "Temirlan" ASJ at a time when respect and honor are being shown to Amir Temur's personality?!

Secondly, Islam in our beliefs are unique. Religious tolerance, humanity, respect for other languages have been raised to the level of a model. However, by inserting the Arabic article al- into the name, inosn does not become religious. Al-Khorazmi, al-Beruni, al-Farabi, al-Bukhari are fine, but "Al-Akram" LLC, "Al-Abdurasul" LLC, "Al-Waris" LLC, "AL-BAOR-AV"

LLC, Names such as "Al-vahid-shifa" LLC, AL-Kamron development LLC also make people think.

Thirdly, the Russian language is considered one of the languages that made a unique contribution to the development of the Uzbek language and its vocabulary. It has its place in our political, social, cultural and spiritual life. However, "Muslimochka", NTM, "Super detki" NTM, "Solnechniy krug" NTM, "Karusel znaniy" NTM, "Ostrov umnix idey" NTM, "Kroshki-nojki" NTM, "Malish herkules" NTM, "Umka IQ" Names like NTM, "Poznavay mir" NTM, Umka cinema also do not serve the development of our native language.

Fourthly, Mama mia, Ya taxi, IQ, Rusvit, Sulfoz, Dinara-pobeda, "Maqom Taom" LLC, "Khamis" JSC, "Bi-lala Service" JSC, "Miss Durдона" JSC, "Buspay" JSC, "Safogoh" sl" XK, "Vabek" OK, "TPNSU" UK means only those working in this organization probably know what they mean. However, according to the naming requirements, the names should be simple, short, express a clear concept, fully meet the rules of the current language, and most importantly, should be easy to use. What can be expected from the name itself "stone nut"?!

Fifth, each name should be written, pronounced, and promoted according to the rules of spelling. Such names as "Uzbekistan-India" friendship society, "*Bashkent uz*" LLC, "*Sherkhan*" JSC, "*Azim-ash-biznes*" JSC, and "*Buhgalteriya-plus*" JSC were not followed.

Results. And now as a fact of our thoughts, we want to share the wonderful semantic structures of popular city names in the world, It's very interesting to you, we think. The city of *Adelaide* in Australia was named after Adelaide, the wife of King William IV of England in 1836.

Bayramali is a city in Turkmenistan. At the end of the 18th century, the ruler of the Mari region was named after Bayramalikhan.

Birobidzhan is a city located in the Far East. It got its name from the fact that it was built at the confluence of the Bira and Bidjan rivers.

Brest is a city in Belarus. Slavic beresta means "white birch bark". Such bark was used in agriculture. Craftsmen made baskets, boxes, cases, ticket kovush (lapti), inscriptions, tableware, sybizz from it. The skin is light and ripe.

Irkutsk is a city in Eastern Siberia. On the banks of the Irkut river, a tributary of the *Angara*. Irqu is derived from the name of an ancient Turkic tribe.

Istanbul is a major port city of Turkey. Ancient names Byzantium, Constantinople, *Sargrad*. The Greeks who wanted to enter the city answered the Turkish border guards: "Is tin polis" (we are going into the city) and this phrase became the name of the city. It was the capital of Turkey in 1918-23.

Karachi is a port city of Pakistan. It was taken from the name of Kulochi tribe. It was the capital of Pakistan in 1947-59.

Quebec is a city in Canada. In one of the Indian languages, it means "place where rivers join".

Leipzig is a city in Germany. This word is related to the name of the Slavic lipa- "linden" tree, which was built in the lap of Lipazor.

St. Petersburg - on May 16, 1703, the city of St. Petersburg (Holy Petersburg) appeared in place of the town of Oreshek on the banks of the Neva River. Peter I named it in honor of Saint Peter.

Los Angeles is a city in the west of the USA. Spanish religious interpretation "city of angels".

Magadan is a city in the Far East. From mongo in the local Orochi language, the word means "sea rocks".

Medina is a city in Saudi Arabia. The Arabic meaning is "city".

Murmansk is a city on the Kola Peninsula. Norwegian Normand is a changed form of the word "Northern man".

New York is a city in the USA. It means "New York". After the British took this city from the Dutch, they named it after the city of York in England, and it was given to the king's brother Duke J. York.

Odessa is a port city in Ukraine. The name of Odessa was given to the newly established western port in 1795, assuming that the ancient Greek address of Odessa was here.

Osaka is one of the largest cities in Japan. In Japanese, osako means "big hill". The city is far above sea level.

Rio de Janeiro is the former capital and largest city of Brazil. On January 1, 1502, Amerigo Vespucci stopped at the mouth of a river and called it Rio de Janeiro - "January river". Later, the city that was founded here was also named that way.

Rotterdam is a city in the Netherlands. It means "dam on the river Rotte".

San Francisco is a port city on the Pacific coast of the United States. It is named after the pirate Francis Drake, who sailed into the cove here in the 16th century.

Saratov is a city on the banks of the Volga. It is formed from the Tatar word sari tov.

Sevastopol is a port city in Ukraine. On the Crimean Peninsula. It means "Royal city" in Greek.

Seoul is the capital of South Korea. The Korean word siegur means "capital city".

Sydney is a city in Australia. It is named after Lord Sidney, an English official, minister of the interior and colonial secretary.

Simferopol is the central city of Crimea region in Ukraine. The old name is Okmachit.

Greek simphero means happy, prosperous, polis means city.

Sochi is a resort city on the Black Sea. The name of the Cherkasy tribe came from Soatshe.

Sukh Bator is a city in Mongolia. It is named after the national hero Sukhe Bator.

Tyumen is one of the old cities of Western Siberia. In old Turkic languages, tuman-ukus means country, region, and at the same time it also means the number of 10,000 people (cavalry). The name of the city comes from the word tuman, which means region, country.

Philadelphia is a city in the USA. His name has a religious meaning. Philadelphia - "city of brotherly love".

Khabarovsk is a city in the Far East. The Russian tourist who reached the Amur River between 1649 and 1651 was named after Yerofei Pavlovich Khabarov.

Cherrapunja is a famous gray city on the southern slopes of the Himalayas. It means "village of hills".

Chita is a city in Eastern Siberia. On the Chita River. In the Evenk language, chita means clay.

Shanghai is a city in China. Shan means mountain, khay means sea, that is, a mountain by the sea.

Yalta is a resort city on the Crimean Peninsula. It is derived from the Greek word lialos- "shore".

Conclusion. As we conclude our viewpoints to the naming of cities and towns, we can say that in generally, the language were given to man to praise God, the Creator, the world and the best qualities in it, to spread it to others. Each national language acquires charm and grace when it was used appropriately within its sphere of influence. Otherwise, it will become dirty and become a dishonorable task in the eyes of the owners who carry it. People who lived in a

certain era owe their language to future generations. This debt cannot be broken by anything. Only attention and a natural "will" to use language are the best tools on this path.

Therefore, attention to the state language, its appropriate use everywhere, not to indulge in artificiality, haste, modernity, and imitation, on the contrary, to give proper names to enterprises and organizations, institutions, all our compatriots, including the head It is a sacred task for the people of Tashkent, who are considered our city. Good luck to all of us on this journey.

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